

D3.1 – Monitoring protocols and methodology for solutions' effectiveness assessment

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Deliverable type	Report
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Reviewed by	Stelios Karozis, S. (NCSR), Valente, M. (UPO), Facci, C. (UPO), Launay, E. (ARIA), Yeterian, G. (ARIA), Comte, A. (UGA), Eychenne, C. (UGA), Rabier, A. (CHUGA)
Dissemination level	Public
Due date	31/08/2025
Actual delivery date	12/09/2025
Version no.	4
Work Package no.	3

Document history		
24/01/2025	Version 1	Encarnação, J. (IRIDEON), Karakitsou, E. (NCSR), López Rodríguez, C. (DEUSTO)
14/05/2025	Version 2	Encarnação, J. (IRIDEON), Karakitsou, E. (NCSR), López Rodríguez, C. (DEUSTO), Representatives of solution providers
22/08/2025	Version 3	
08/09/2025	Version 4	

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Project partners

Acronym	Full Name of Organisation
AIM	Municipality Of Alba Iulia
AMT	Amt Der Tiroler Landesregierung
ARIA	Aria Technologies Sas
CHUGA	Centre Hospitalier Universitaire De Grenoble
CRISISOFT	Crisisoft
CSTB	Centre Scientifique Et Technique Du Batiment
CTP	Consortio De La Comunidad De Trabajo De Los Pirineos
DAS	Directia De Asistenta Sociala
ENERGAP	Energetsko Podnebna Agencija Za Podravje
EQY	Euroquality
FLORALIS	Floralis
GAM	Grenoble-Alpes-Metropole Metro
HAM	Freie Und Hansestadt Hamburg
HCWHE	Health Care Without Harm Europe
HCM	Zdravstveni Dom Dr Adolfa Drolca Maribor
HWWI	Hamburgisches Weltwirtschaftsinstitut Gemeinnutzige Gmbh
IRIDEON	Irideon SI
NCSR	National Center For Scientific Research "Demokritos"
SELNICA	Obcina Selnica Ob Dravi
SCJUT	Spitalul Clinic Judetean De Urgenta Pius Brinzeu Timisoara
TIKLI	Tirol Kliniken Gmbh
UDEUSTO	Universidad De La Iglesia De Deusto Entidad Religiosa
UGA	Universite Grenoble Alpes
UMIT	Umit Tirol - Private Universitat Fur Gesundheitswissenschaften Und Technologie Gmbh
UPO	Universita Degli Studi Del Piemonte Orientale Amedeo Avogadro

Acronyms

EWE – Extreme Weather Event

IEQ – Indoor environmental quality

KPI – Key Performance Indicator

LMS - Learning Management System

NGO – Non-Governmental Organisation

PR – Project Result

TADA - TransformAr Avoided Damages framework and application

TNA – Training Needs Assessment

Introduction

This deliverable reports on the monitoring protocols and methodology for all solutions' effectiveness assessment, including the trainings, alongside the methodology that needs to be followed for being effective in demonstration sites, and the collection of information to tailor the existing TransformAr Avoided Damages framework and application (TADA).

The deliverable is divided in three sections:

- A. Monitoring protocols and methodology
- B. Preparation of the methodology for the evaluation of training
- C. Tailoring of the Impact Assessment framework and application

The monitoring protocols and methodology for evaluating each of the solutions based on the KPIs defined in T1.1.1 and reported in D1.1, were designed. The defined KPIs not only support the monitoring protocols establishment (T3.2), but will also be used in the assessment of the solutions' effectiveness (T3.4).

The KPI based monitoring and assessment methodology was created for each specific solution co-developed and co-designed under Task 2.2 and reported in D2.2.

The monitoring stems from listing information on the KPIs (Section A1) selected for each solution, and the relevance of each KPI (Section A1), i.e. why each was chosen for monitoring purposes.

The methodology to assess each solution is setup under the umbrella of each KPI:

- i) How these affect the project within the 5Ws + H scope (who, what, where, when, why and how).
- ii) How to specifically measure the success or failure of each KPI.
- iii) Define how to affect each KPI positively and ensure that the targets are met.

The monitoring protocols and methodology for evaluating each of the solutions based on the KPIs will support the execution of Tasks 3.3 and 3.4 to be reported in D3.2.

The proper implementation and use of the solutions at the demo sites, required the design and implementation of a comprehensive training programme (Task 1.4). This lead to Training Co-creation Activities detailed in the Deliverable 2.4, outlining the co-created multidisciplinary training programme, detailing the training sessions aimed at

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enhancing the ability to mitigate, adapt, and resiliently respond to climate threats in pilot regions.

The methodology for the monitoring and evaluation of the satisfaction, processes and results of the micro-courses are detailed in this deliverable, in a 4 steps evaluation: (1) Ex-ante evaluation, (2) Intermediary evaluation, (3) Final evaluation, (4) Drafting of the final document. A set of tools including the methodology, templates for the surveys and questionnaires were designed to evaluate the trainings.

To tailor the existing TransformAr Avoided Damages framework and application (TADA) solution, relevant hazards and quantifiable KPIs were identified for each solution (based on what was defined in T1.1), with an assessment of the quantifiable KPIs that can be affected due to Climate Change. This information will be integrated these in the web-based application that allow users to find the most relevant solution based on a multicriteria selection. This will deliver the first version of the Impact assessment application (PR7) that will be tested in T3.4 and included in the Full Guide.

A. Monitoring protocols and methodology

The monitoring protocols and methodology are designed for the assessment of the good implementation and exploitation of the solutions. This will be supervised by partner UGA, supported by each of the solution providers and each demonstration site partner.

Each solution is unique, with different value propositions, functionalities, requirements, specifications, systems, architectures, and logistics. The methodology consists on having each solution provider training the end-users of each demo site on: i) the use of the solutions, and ii) on the interpretation and use of the solution specific monitoring protocols based on selected KPIs. The demo site partner will have to be able to autonomously use the solutions to perform the pertinent assessment data collection based on this deliverable.

The Demo site partners will need to clearly understand:

- 1- The selected KPIs used to monitor each solution. Each KPI was selected by each solution provider as a representative monitoring indicator.
- 2- The relevance of each KPI for the Solution. Each KPI covers a very specific aspect related to the nature of the solution. This will reveal how it fits to the needs and particular conditions of each demo site, and thus why each was chosen for monitoring purposes. Some KPIs may not fit in the testing scenario of a demo site.
- 3- How each KPI affects the project within the 5Ws + H scope (who, what, where, when, why and how). This information will be the main methodological guide for the demo site partners, to: i) perceive the circumstances under which each KPI must be tackled for the assessment of the solution, and ii) the required elements to collect the necessary assessment data. This will also ease the adaptation of each solution to the specificities of each demo site.
- 4- How to specifically measure the success or failure of each KPI. This covers the exact type and nature of data that needs to be collected for a successful assessment of the performance of the solution.
- 5- Define how to affect each KPI positively and ensure that the targets are met. This provides supplementary information on good practices, which will ensure that the demo site partners use the solutions according to proper requirements

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and specifications. This will increase the chances of successfully collecting the data needed for the correct assessment of the performance of the solution.

1. Monitoring- KPIs related to the Solution

1.1 VECTRACK- IRIDEON

KPI 1- Number of total mosquitos caught.

KPI 2 - Number of detected peaks of mosquito activity.

KPI 3 - Incidence of mosquito-borne diseases (e.g., Dengue, WNV, Malaria) in mosquito and human populations.

KPI 4 - Mosquito-borne disease infections abroad or in Demo site: imported vs autochthonous cases.

KPI 5 - Detection of mosquitos and eggs/larvae in breeding sites, performed by field technicians.

KPI 6 - Data from mosquito alerts (sightings, bites, breeding sites).

1.2 Indoor environmental quality (IEQ) monitoring method- CSTB

KPI 1- Thermal environment

KPI 2 - Indoor air quality

KPI 3 - Indoor air resilience

1.3 SURVIVAL- UMIT

KPI 1 - Vector Modelling

KPI 2 - Climatic Data

KPI 3 - Simulation Scenarios

KPI 4 - Analysis and Visualization of Scenarios

1.4 SENTINEL - ARIA

KPI 1 – Real-time monitoring of air pollution exposure.

KPI 2 – Air pollution exposure forecast.

KPI 3 – Allergenic pollen peak detection through real-time monitoring.

KPI 4 – Critical periods for air quality.

KPI 5 – Ragweed pollen sources mapping.

1.5 LIFE RESYSTAL ecosystem- NCSR

KPI 1- Number of climate risk assessments conducted.

KPI 2 - Vulnerability level of different locations and per category.

KPI 3 - Impact level of different locations and per category.

KPI 4 - Risk level of different locations and per category.

1.6 MenKorn CALL- CRISISOFT

KPI 1- Device – Situation information

KPI 2 – Device - Areas & managers

KPI 3 – Device - Number of Accounts Alerted

KPI 4 – Device – Territorial impact

KPI 5 – Handrail – Statistics

KPI 6 – Handrail – Journal

KPI 7 – Staff – Profiles of committed and operational staff

KPI 8 – Vehicles – Stock

1.7 Disaster preparedness checklist- UPO

KPI 1 – User-perceived accuracy level of the Checklist in identifying items that are lacking or suboptimal for disaster preparedness

KPI 2 – Time spent for filling up the Checklist

KPI 3 – Percentage increase in disaster preparedness awareness amongst users of the Checklist

1.8 Physical activity recommendations- UGA

KPI 1- Levels of air pollution in high-traffic areas such as cycle paths and sports facilities.

KPI 2 - Temperature measurements at frequently visited locations like cycle paths and sports facilities.

KPI 3 - Number of participants involved in testing the proposed solution. (Computed for Grenoble demonstration site).

KPI 4 - Number of participants in the panel for recommendations co-creation (Health experts, local actors and citizens).

KPI 5 - Number of recommendations validated by the panel of experts.

2. Monitoring- Relevance of each KPI for the Solution

2.1- VECTRACK- IRIDEON

- **KPI 1- Number of total mosquitos caught**

Mosquito abundance is important because it directly relates to the risk of mosquito-borne diseases, which pose a significant public health challenge. Acquiring the number of captured mosquitoes per trap, helps understanding the field situation on mosquito populations and identify areas at higher risk, leading to better informed, timely and cost-effective control measures.

- **KPI 2- Number of detected peaks of mosquito activity**

Different mosquito species have varying activity patterns and preferences, with some being more active during the day and others at night. Mosquito populations tend to increase during warmer months, but their activity is also influenced by other factors like humidity and rainfall. While the detection of mosquito activity peaks during the year is a crucial factor in determining the best time to implement control measures for mosquitoes, the time of day when a particular species peaks also significantly contributes to the effectiveness of mosquito control efforts.

- **KPI 3- Incidence of mosquito-borne diseases (e.g., Dengue, WNV, Malaria) in mosquito and human populations**

Mosquito-borne diseases like Dengue, West Nile Virus (WNV), and Malaria pose significant public health concerns, with varying levels of incidence in mosquito and human populations. Mosquitoes acquire pathogens (viruses, parasites, or bacteria) by feeding on the blood of infected individuals or animals. They then transmit these pathogens to other hosts, like humans, through their saliva when biting.

- **KPI 4- Mosquito-borne disease infections abroad or in Demo site: imported vs autochthonous cases**

In the context of mosquito-borne diseases, the term "imported cases" refers to infections where a person has travelled to a region where the disease is endemic, become infected, and then returned to a location where the disease is not typically found. Autochthonous cases are infections that occur within a region where the vector (mosquito) is present, and the disease is transmitted locally.

- **KPI 5- Detection of mosquitos and eggs/larvae in breeding sites, performed by field technicians**

Mosquitoes primarily breed in standing water. Common breeding sites include: gutters, birdbaths, pet bowls, old tires, plant saucers, and even small containers of water. They also use artificial containers like buckets and trash cans, as well as natural containers like tree holes and leaf axils.

To effectively destroy breeding sites, and reduce mosquito populations, the focus must be on eliminating standing water in and around areas where peaks of mosquito adult population, or relevant adult abundance, are detected. This can involve removing or modifying containers that hold water, regularly cleaning and emptying containers, and preventing water from accumulating in certain areas.

- **KPI 6- Data from mosquito alerts (sightings, bites, breeding sites)**

Citizens can significantly contribute to mosquito control by actively participating in efforts to eliminate breeding sites and raise awareness in their communities. This includes removing standing water, using mosquito repellents, and reporting suspected mosquito infestations or unusual mosquito species.

Community reports of mosquito sighs, bites and breeding sites, can be of very relevant importance, and citizens can use free applications to make their contribution. For instance, “Mosquito Alert” (<https://www.mosquitoalert.com/en/>) is a citizen science project that allows anyone to report mosquito sightings and breeding sites via a free app, providing valuable data for public health.

2.2 Indoor environmental quality (IEQ) monitoring method- CSTB

- **KPI 1- Thermal environment**

The indoor environmental quality (IEQ) monitoring solution will provide continuous measurements of indoor air temperature and relative humidity, allowing the thermal environment to be assessed against the guideline values.

- **KPI 2- Indoor air quality**

The IEQ monitoring solution will provide continuous or punctual measurements of indoor air pollutant concentrations, allowing the indoor air quality to be assessed against the guideline values.

- **KPI 3- Indoor air resilience**

Indoor air resilience to specific extreme weather events can be assessed using the parameters measured to assess KPI1 and KPI2 during relevant periods, e.g., heat waves and high outdoor pollution.

2.3 SURVIVAL- UMIT

- **KPI 1- Vector Modelling**

The modelling of disease vectors such as *Aedes aegypti*, the main vector of Dengue, Zika and Chikungunya viruses, is a key tool in epidemiological research and prevention. For this reason, this first model was examined and the relevant scientific literature and biological data were extracted. From this, a model was developed that describes a cycle from the egg to the mosquito within its natural habitat. This model was then implemented in the Survival simulation package in the Java programming language. The mathematical and computer-based model can thus help to simulate the spread of this mosquito species under different environmental conditions. Factors such as temperature, humidity, precipitation as well as human behaviour and urbanization are taken into account. The aim of the modelling is to identify risk areas at an early stage, predict outbreaks and plan targeted control measures.

- **KPI 2- Climatic Data**

For the modelling, daily updated climate data from GeoSphere Austria is used, which is available for the province of Tyrol in annual resolution freely. The data sets include meteorological parameters such as air temperature, relative humidity, precipitation, solar radiation and other climate-relevant variables. This information is integrated into the model in order to realistically depict the location- and time-dependent development of *Aedes aegypti*. The use of high-resolution climate data makes it possible to analyse the effects of specific weather conditions on vector dynamics in a differentiated manner and to make them usable for forecasting purposes.

- **KPI 3- Simulation Scenarios**

As part of the modelling, various scenarios are considered in order to analyse the potential spread and establishment of *Aedes aegypti* under varying environmental conditions. One focus is on the immigration of the mosquito population through traffic and transportation routes. In addition, the suitability of different settlement structures as potential breeding and resting habitats is included in the modelling.

The life cycle of the vector depicted in the model - from egg to larva and pupa to adult - is simulated as a function of temperature. This is based on the daily climate data stored in the database, in particular the temperature curves.

Hypothetical temperature scenarios are also modelled to evaluate possible climatic developments. For example, annual mean temperatures are increased by +1.5 °C and +2.5 °C (e.g.) in order to investigate the effects on the population dynamics and overwintering potential of *Aedes aegypti* under changed climate conditions. This scenario-based approach allows a forward-looking assessment of possible risks in the course of climate change.

In addition to scenario modelling of climatic and infrastructural influencing factors, the model simulates various strategies for controlling and containing *Aedes aegypti*. These include measures such as targeted control of larval habitats, use of biological control methods, reduction of artificial water accumulations in residential areas and potential restrictions on vector transport along traffic corridors.

The effectiveness of these strategies will be simulated under different climatic conditions and dispersal scenarios.

The aim is to quantitatively assess the effectiveness of individual or combined measures and to derive scientifically sound recommendations for integrated vector management in Tyrol. In this way, practical scenarios can be developed for emergencies and decision-makers can receive evidence-based support.

- **KPI 4- Analysis and Visualization of Scenarios**

QGIS is used to visualize the results spatially. This allows both the climate data and the modelled occurrences and development stages of the vector to be mapped and visualized. This supports the identification of potential risk areas and serves as a basis for targeted measures in vector control.

All modelled scenarios - including climatic changes, habitat distributions, immigration pathways and the tested mitigation strategies - are comprehensively evaluated using statistical software. Descriptive and inferential statistical methods are used to quantify differences between scenarios and to identify relationships between environmental factors and vector behaviour.

The results of these analyses form the basis for the creation of standardized reports in which key findings are summarized, risks are assessed and specific recommendations for action are derived. The aim is to provide well-founded assessments of the future development of the *Aedes aegypti* population in Tyrol and to provide an evidence-

based decision-making basis for authorities, the healthcare system and local authorities.

2.4 SENTINEL - ARIA

- **KPI 1- Real-time monitoring of air pollution exposure**

This indicator deals with the outdoor air quality measurements, specifically at health care centre. The real time data are linked to alerts in case the threshold is exceeded. These real-time alerts are essential to protect vulnerable patients and staff, and to trigger immediate health recommendations.

- **KPI 2- Air pollution exposure forecast.**

Based on forecast modelling of atmospheric dispersion, this indicator anticipates short-term pollution episodes. It can be used to alert healthcare professionals in advance, to adapt treatment schedules and to predict a possible increase in consultations for respiratory pathologies. This capacity for anticipation is a strategic lever for managing health care resources and prevention.

- **KPI 3- Allergenic pollen peak detection through real-time monitoring.**

This indicator is based on continuous measurements of pollen concentration (particularly ragweed), available on a platform. It can be used to rapidly detect allergen peaks on an urban scale, alert health establishments and recommend protective measures for sensitive patients. It helps to limit the acute health effects of respiratory allergies.

- **KPI 4- Critical periods for air quality.**

Real-time measurements (air pollutants, pollen) will be stored to perform an analysis of past data and identify critical periods (for air quality and pollens). This indicator is useful for tailoring air treatment devices and hospital practices and explore future strategies to reduce exposure.

- **KPI 5- Ragweed pollen sources mapping.**

Identification of local ragweed plants through analysis of stored real-time pollen peak data will be explored. This detection supports timely environmental actions such as mowing or revegetation. It also informs long-term strategies to reduce public exposure to allergens.

2.5 LIFE RESYSTAL ecosystem- NCSR D

- **KPI 1- Number of climate risk assessments conducted.**

For each area climate change is being affected by many different climate stressors and hazards. The latter means that different climate risk assessment (one per hazard) should be conducted in order to provide a holistic estimation on how the health facility may be affected due to climate change. Moreover, the same logic applies for the different climate scenarios. The latter is important not only for the levels of risk per scenario, but providing to the health facility operators the range of risk assessment “solutions” due to the uncertainty of climate change.

- **KPI 2 - Vulnerability level of different locations and per category.**

Vulnerability per hazard provides the vulnerable points on the infrastructure and pinpoints the location of interventions, alongside the relevant actors that need to be involved.

- **KPI 3 - Impact level of different locations and per category.**

Impact level is correlated to a specific scenario and level of intensity of hazard. As such, it provides a very customized information of how the infrastructure or the part of infrastructure will potentially be affected.

- **KPI 4 - Risk level of different locations and per category.**

Risk combines the level of impact alongside the change of frequency of climate hazard under assessment. As such, it provides a combined measure to help estimate the location and urgency of interventions that are necessary for climate proofing.

2.6 MenKorn CALL- CRISISOFT

- **KPI 1- Device - Situation information**

This indicator is updated with each new Status Update. Each new status report generates a notification. The fields affected by a modification display the new data in black, and the old data, which have become obsolete, are crossed out, in red.

In this part, you find: location, weather report, traffic, Dominant issues, Observations, Services committed, victims by category (estimated, Deceased, Absolute emergencies, Related emergencies, involved), Activated Plan, Other information (team commitment, Crisis room, drug batch, possible development, risk of development).

- **KPI 2- Device - Areas & managers**

This indicator deals with the general configuration of the device.

The cartography: Mapping that geolocates the zones and establishments impacted by the device.

Tip : Mapping is interactive: zoom, full-screen display and choice of information to be displayed.

The Table: Real-time summary of the location of zones and those responsible for the device.

- **KPI 3- Device - Number of Accounts Alerted**

This indicator deals with alerts disseminated to managers of facility departments and institutional partners.

The graph: Donut of colours according to the services alerted. Each segment represents the number of individual accounts alerted for each department. The indicator in the centre specifies the total number of alerts broadcast.

The Table: Real-time summary of alerts distributed to each service and to people who have accessed the observatory information.

- **KPI 4- Device – Territorial impact**

This indicator deals with the impact of the crisis by municipality

The graph: Histogram of colours according to communes impacted. Each column represents the impact of the event on each commune. A different colour is associated with each impacted facility.

The Table: Real-time summary of communes impacted, with details of establishments and services concerned.

- **KPI 5- Handrail – Statistics**

This indicator deals with handrail entries made by all operators of the device. A handrail entry is a handwritten entry of text information. Each entry is themed.

The graph: Donut of colours according to handrail themes. The outer circle represents the proportion of entries by theme. The inner circle represents the distribution of these thematic entries made by the various departments.

The Table: Real-time synthesis of the different handrail entries by theme and service.

- **KPI 6- Handrail – Journal**

This element allows you to see the handrails history (time, author, level, message) and add entries if necessary.

- **KPI 7- Staff – Profiles of committed and operational staff**

This indicator deals with the distribution of personnel hired and arriving in their department or zone, for the event and according to their professional profiles.

The graph:

Profiles committed and arrived: Coloured donut based on job profiles. Each sector represents the proportion of the number of personnel hired and arriving on a job profile.

Staff evolution: Coloured curves based on job profiles. Each curve represents the evolution of the number of personnel hired and arriving on a job profile.

Tip : The filter at the top of the graph allows you to display/hide certain job profiles.

The Table: Real-time summary by zone and department of the job profiles hired and arrived and any specialties available.

- **KPI 8- Vehicles – Stock**

This indicator deals with all vehicles (ambulatory and others) engaged on the event according to their types.

The graph: Colour curves according to vector type. Each curve represents the evolution of the number of vectors involved.

Tip : The filter at the top of the graph allows you to show/hide certain types of vectors.

The Table: Real-time summary by zone of the types of vectors engaged.

2.7 Disaster preparedness checklist- UPO

Objective: to facilitate the monitoring of the health system's preparedness and to provide guidance for decision-makers, ultimately aiming to enhance health emergency management in the context of Extreme Weather Events (EWEs).

- **KPI 1 – User-perceived accuracy level of the Checklist in identifying items that are lacking or suboptimal for disaster preparedness**

This KPI is relevant for assessing the effectiveness of the Checklist in accurately identifying items that are lacking or suboptimal for disaster preparedness in the health system where it is implemented. A high accuracy level ensures that critical gaps are correctly detected, enabling targeted interventions. Improvements in accuracy over time indicate improvements in the Checklist's ability to capture disaster preparedness in the health systems where it is implemented.

- **KPI 2 – Time spent for filling up the Checklist**

This KPI is relevant for assessing the efficiency of the disaster preparedness evaluation process. A high amount of time spent indicates potential inefficiencies or complexities in the Checklist, while a decreasing trend suggests improvements in the process, likely due to better understanding. By monitoring this KPI, the Checklist can be optimized, leading to quicker and more effective assessments of disaster preparedness.

- **KPI 3 – User-perceived increase in disaster preparedness awareness after using the Checklist**

This KPI is relevant for measuring the impact of the Checklist on users' awareness of disaster preparedness. An increase in awareness indicates that the Checklist is effectively highlighting key preparedness concepts, while a stagnant or decreasing percentage suggests the need for improvement. By tracking this KPI, the effectiveness of the Checklist in enhancing awareness can be evaluated.

2.8 Physical activity recommendations- UGA

- **KPI 1: Levels of air pollution in high-traffic areas such as cycle paths and sports facilities.**

Air pollution measurements will be collected through the clinical research protocol attached to our solution. These measurements are important in order to quantify the levels of pollutants that our participants are exposure to during physical activity.

- **KPI 2: Temperature measurements at frequently visited locations like cycle paths and sports facilities.**

Local authorities have 150 temperature sensors spread across the city with data that we can collect. This is important in order to qualify the heat category on the days physiological and air quality data is collected in order to formulate our physical activity recommendations.

- **KPI 3: Number of participants involved in testing the proposed solution.**

A sample of approximately one hundred participants, each contributing a minimum of two sessions, would ensure a representative diversity of situations and generate a sufficient volume of data for the planned statistical analyses.

- **KPI 4: Number of participants in the panel for recommendations co-creation (Health experts, local actors and citizens).**

To allow the development of realistic and actionable recommendations for physical activity during periods of peak pollution and heatwaves, especially for vulnerable people, a group of stakeholder are bring together.

- **KPI 5 – Number of recommendations validated by the panel of experts**

These recommendations provide an evidence-based framework to help individuals make informed decisions about engaging in physical activity under conditions of air pollution and heat stress, two major environmental risk factors that can significantly impact health and performance.

3. Assessment: 5Ws + H scope (who, what, where, when, why and how)

3.1- VECTRACK- IRIDEON

- **KPI 1- Number of total mosquitos caught**

WHO

Technicians responsible for mosquito surveillance and control.

WHAT

Determine mosquito abundance in a given area.

WHERE

Chosen sampling sites adequate to monitor mosquito activity.

WHEN

During mosquito season.

WHY

To quantify the abundance of mosquito populations of species of potential risk.

HOW

Using VECTRACK smart traps (automatic counts) or standard commercial traps (manual counts).

- **KPI 2- Number of detected peaks of mosquito activity**

WHO

Technicians responsible for mosquito surveillance and control.

WHAT

Determine mosquito dynamics in a given area.

WHERE

Chosen sampling sites adequate to monitor mosquito activity.

WHEN

During mosquito season.

WHY

To quantify the growth and detect peaks of activity of mosquito populations of species of potential risk.

HOW

Using VECTRACK smart traps (automatic counts) or standard commercial traps (manual counts).

- **KPI 3- Incidence of mosquito-borne diseases (e.g., Dengue, WNV, Malaria) in mosquito and human populations**

WHO

Technicians responsible for mosquito surveillance and control, and public health bodies.

WHAT

Detect the presence of mosquito borne pathogens in mosquito and human populations.

WHERE

Chosen sampling sites adequate to monitor mosquito activity.

WHEN

During mosquito season.

WHY

To make an early identification of the mosquito borne diseases that could potentially affect the human population.

HOW

Collecting mosquito samples from traps which are analysed in laboratory, and information published by health authorities on mosquito-borne diseases detected in the human population.

- **KPI 4- Mosquito-borne disease infections abroad or in Demo site: imported vs autochthonous cases**

WHO

Public health bodies.

WHAT

Detect the presence of mosquito borne pathogens in travellers (imported cases) and local citizens that have not travelled or have not been in contact with infected travellers (autochthonous cases).

WHERE

Public health facilities.

WHEN

During mosquito season.

WHY

To make an early identification of infected citizens that could potentially be patient zero of a potential mosquito borne disease outbreak.

HOW

Information published by health authorities on mosquito-borne diseases detected in travellers of local citizens.

- **KPI 5- Detection of mosquitos and eggs/larvae in breeding sites, performed by field technicians**

WHO

Technicians responsible for mosquito surveillance and control.

WHAT

Detect breeding sites that can contribute to increased mosquito activity (abundance and peaks).

WHERE

Chosen sampling sites adequate to monitor mosquito activity, and surroundings. Areas of activity of volunteer citizens that gather information.

WHEN

During mosquito season.

WHY

To make an early detection of breeding sites that should be destroyed.

HOW

Using VECTRACK smart traps (automatic counts) or standard commercial traps (manual counts) to detect increased abundance and peaks of activity that indicate the nearby presence of critical breeding sites. Using free apps like “Mosquito Alert” to consult citizen reports.

- **KPI 6- Data from mosquito alerts (sightings, bites, breeding sites)**

WHO

Citizens.

WHAT

Detect mosquito activity with a higher spatial resolution.

WHERE

Areas of activity of volunteer citizens that gather information.

WHEN

During mosquito season.

WHY

Acquire mosquito data that complements the data obtained from traps.

HOW

Using free apps like “Mosquito Alert”.

3.2 Indoor environmental quality (IEQ) monitoring method- CSTB

- **KPI 1- Thermal environment**

WHO

Owners, operators, and occupants of healthcare facilities.

WHAT

Thermal environment against guideline values.

WHERE

Healthcare facilities.

WHEN

Heat waves, cold waves, or other relevant periods.

WHY

To ensure the health and well-being of the building occupants.

HOW

Evaluation based on measurements.

- **KPI 2- Indoor air quality**

WHO

Owners, operators, and occupants of healthcare facilities.

WHAT

Indoor air quality against guideline values.

WHERE

Healthcare facilities.

WHEN

Heat waves, cold waves, or other relevant periods.

WHY

To ensure the health and well-being of the building occupants.

HOW

Evaluation based on measurements.

- **KPI 3- Indoor air resilience**

WHO

Owners, operators, and occupants of healthcare facilities.

WHAT

Indoor air resilience to extreme weather events.

WHERE

Healthcare facilities.

WHEN

Heat waves, cold waves, or other relevant periods.

WHY

To ensure the functionality of the building's indoor environment

HOW

Evaluation based on measurements.

3.3 SURVIVAL- UMIT

WHO

Project team and researchers: define and monitor KPIs to assess model quality and scenario predictions.

Health authorities and decision-makers: receive evidence-based assessments based on the KPIs.

Public health stakeholders: use the results to plan measures against vectors.

WHAT

KPIs evaluate the model quality and informative value as well as the effectiveness of tested scenarios.

Accuracy of the vector distribution models; Response time of the system to changes in climate data; Effectiveness of individual containment strategies; Increase or decrease in potential populations under temperature scenarios; Spatial correspondence between model and real risk areas

WHERE

In the entire modelling environment, including climate data integration, habitat classification, population dynamics and visualization.

In the analysis and reporting system, where the results are output at regional level (e.g. Tyrol).

WHEN

Already during model development to ensure validity.

During the simulation of climate scenarios and action strategies (ongoing monitoring).

At the end of each simulation round to ensure comparability.

During final evaluation and reporting to justify recommendations based on data.

WHY

To ensure that the model makes reliable and comprehensible statements about vector behaviour under climatic and structural changes.

To quantitatively validate risk assessments and recommended measures.

To make the effectiveness of mitigation scenarios measurable.

To be able to objectively evaluate comparisons between scenarios.

HOW

The evaluation is quantitative and statistical, supplemented by spatial analyses in QGIS.

The KPIs could flow into reports and decision-making tools and support the derivation of specific recommendations for public health.

3.4 SENTINEL - ARIA

- **KPI 1- Real-time monitoring of air pollution exposure.**

WHO

Patients, health care staff, emergency services.

WHAT

Real-time monitoring of pollution.

WHERE

Grenoble hospital site, and Alba Iulia city

WHEN

All year round, with peaks in summer (ozone) and winter (PM).

WHY

Protect sensitive populations and adapt care.

HOW

Automatic alerts using AQ KUNAK sensors for Grenoble and Urad Monitor sensors for Alba Iulia

- **KPI 2- Air pollution exposure forecast.**

WHO

Patients, health care staff, emergency services.

WHAT

Short-term air quality forecast.

WHERE

Grenoble hospital site, and Alba Iulia city

WHEN

Daily

WHY

Anticipate peaks in order to adjust services.

HOW

Air pollution alerts using atmospheric dispersion forecast model.

- **KPI 3- Allergenic pollen peak detection through real-time monitoring.**

WHO

Allergy sufferers, health care staff.

WHAT

Ragweed pollen peak measured.

WHERE

Grenoble city

WHEN

Mainly from August to September (pollen season)

WHY

Anticipate allergy-related emergency consultations.

HOW

Alerts based on Aerotape pollen measurements from Oberon.

- **KPI 4- Critical periods for air quality.**

WHO

Health care staff, local authorities.

WHAT

Identification of critical periods (air quality, pollen).

WHERE

Grenoble hospital site and Alba Iulia city

WHEN

Yearly analysis

WHY

Highlight critical periods for environmental management action.

HOW

Analysis of air quality forecast and measurements.

- **KPI 5- Ragweed pollen sources mapping.**

WHO

Allergy sufferers, health care staff, local authorities.

WHAT

Identification of ragweed plants when pollen measurements are available.

WHERE

Grenoble city

WHEN

Seasonal analysis

WHY

Highlight local ragweed plants that may be causing an allergy season.

HOW

Analysis of pollen measurements.

3.5 LIFE RESYSTAL ecosystem- NCSR

- **KPI 1- Number of climate risk assessments conducted.**

WHO

Health facility operators, technicians, engineers.

WHAT

-

WHERE

-

WHEN

Anytime

WHY

Provides an estimation of the level of uncertainty.

HOW

In LIFE RESYSTAL platform

- **KPI 2 - Vulnerability level of different locations and per category.**

WHO

Health facility operators, technicians, engineers.

WHAT

-

WHERE

-

WHEN

Anytime

WHY

Provides the vulnerable points of infrastructure.

HOW

In LIFE RESYSTAL platform.

- **KPI 3 - Impact level of different locations and per category.**

WHO

Health facility operators, technicians, engineers.

WHAT

-

WHERE

-

WHEN

Anytime

WHY

Provides the impact level and impact list of the infrastructure.

HOW

In LIFE RESYSTAL platform.

- **KPI 4 - Risk level of different locations and per category.**

WHO

Health facility operators, technicians, engineers.

WHAT

-

WHERE

-

WHEN

Anytime

WHY

Provides the risk level of infrastructure enabling to take intervention decisions

HOW

In LIFE RESYSTAL platform.

3.6 MenKorn CALL- CRISISOFT

- **KPI 1- Device – Situation information**

WHO

Anyone involved (key people and partners) in the crisis who has a strategic position in crisis management.

WHAT

Information on the crisis: location, weather conditions, road traffic, dominant issues, observation, estimated number of victims by category, type of crisis plan activated, number of teams involved, crisis room activated, batch of medication used, possible evolution and risk of development.

WHERE

On the scene of the crisis.

WHEN

Each time a situation is reviewed.

WHY

To keep key personnel and partners informed of the situation.

HOW

Information by notification: e-mail, SMS, voice message.

- **KPI 2- Device - Areas & managers**

WHO

Anyone involved (key people and partners) in the crisis who has a strategic position in crisis management.

WHAT

Gives geolocation of the system in place and the hospital involved.

WHERE

On the scene of the crisis.

WHEN

Real time.

WHY

To give key personnel and partners visibility of the system in place.

HOW

By displaying a map or table showing the different operational zones.

- **KPI 3- Device - Number of Accounts Alerted**

WHO

Anyone involved (key people and partners) in the crisis who has a strategic position in crisis management.

WHAT

Gives an indication of the number of people (key people and partner) alerted to connect to the crisis observatory.

WHERE

On the scene of the crisis.

WHEN

Real time.

WHY

To give an indication of the number of people alerted.

HOW

Information by notification: e-mail, SMS, voice message.

- **KPI 4- Device – Territorial impact**

WHO

Anyone involved (key people and partners) in the crisis who has a strategic position in crisis management.

WHAT

Gives the territorial impact of healthcare facilities involved in the crisis.

WHERE

On the scene of the crisis.

WHEN

Real time.

WHY

To give the geographical area of influence of a crisis.

HOW

Graph or table

- **KPI 5- Handrail – Statistics**

WHO

Anyone involved (key people and partners) in the crisis who has a strategic position in crisis management.

WHAT

This indicator deals with handrail entries made by all operators of the device.

WHERE

On the scene of the crisis.

WHEN

Real time.

WHY

Shows the themes exchanged, the number of exchanges and the author of the entry.

HOW

Graph or table

- **KPI 6- Handrail – Journal**

WHO

Anyone involved (key people and partners) in the crisis who has a strategic position in crisis management.

WHAT

This element allows you to see the handrails history.

WHERE

On the scene of the crisis.

WHEN

Real time.

WHY

View the various exchanges made by whom and when.

HOW

List

- **KPI 7- Staff – Profiles of committed and operational staff**

WHO

Anyone involved (key people and partners) in the crisis who has a strategic position in crisis management.

WHAT

Gives an indication of the different business profiles involved in the crisis.

WHERE

On the scene of the crisis.

WHEN

Real time.

WHY

To visualize device sizing.

HOW

Graph or table

- **KPI 8- Vehicles – Stock**

WHO

Anyone involved (key people and partners) in the crisis who has a strategic position in crisis management.

WHAT

Gives an indication of the different vehicles involved in the crisis.

WHERE

On the scene of the crisis.

WHEN

Real time.

WHY

To visualize device sizing.

HOW

Graph or table

3.7 Disaster preparedness checklist- UPO

- **KPI 1 – User-perceived accuracy level of the Checklist in identifying items that are lacking or suboptimal for disaster preparedness**

WHO

The solution providers.

WHAT

The user-perceived accuracy level of the Checklist.

WHERE

This KPI is measured at first in the Mountadapt demonstration and replication sites where the Checklist is implemented; subsequently, in every other site that is willing to test the Checklist.

WHEN

This KPI is measured periodically each time the Checklist is completed.

WHY

This KPI can highlight perceived accuracy issues, assess baseline reliability, and inform improvements by guiding targeted interventions (e.g: refinement by the solution provider).

HOW

A short survey, accessible via a link embedded in the Checklist, will be used to measure this KPI. The survey will include a question assessing user-perceived accuracy in capturing disaster preparedness, with responses recorded on a numerical scale.

- **KPI 2 – Time spent for filling up the Checklist**

WHO

The solution providers.

WHAT

The efficiency and usability of the Checklist.

WHERE

This KPI is measured at first in the Mountadapt demonstration and replication sites where the Checklist is implemented; subsequently, in every other site that is willing to test the Checklist.

WHEN

This KPI is measured periodically each time the Checklist is completed.

WHY

Helps optimise the Checklist design and usability, reducing administrative burden, improving adoption and encouraging use.

HOW

A short survey, accessible via a link embedded in the Checklist, will be used to measure this KPI. The survey will include a question on the approximate time required to complete the Checklist.

- **KPI 3 – User-perceived increase in disaster preparedness awareness after using the Checklist**

WHO

The solution providers.

WHAT

Improvement in user-perceived disaster preparedness awareness after using the Checklist.

WHERE

This KPI is measured at first in the Mountadapt demonstration and replication sites where the Checklist is implemented; subsequently, in every other site that is willing to test the Checklist.

WHEN

This KPI should be measured periodically each time the Checklist is completed.

WHY

Ensures that the Checklist is effectively enhancing awareness.

HOW

A short survey, accessible via a link embedded in the Checklist, will be used to measure this KPI. The survey will include a question on the approximate time required to complete the Checklist.

3.8 Physical activity recommendations- UGA

- **KPI 1: Levels of air pollution in high-traffic areas such as cycle paths and sports facilities.**

WHO

The general population

WHAT

Levels of air pollution.

WHERE

In high-traffic areas such as cycle paths and sports facilities.

WHEN

During daytime hours.

WHY

To evaluate the exposure to air pollution in those areas

HOW

Sensors

- **KPI 2: Temperature measurements at frequently visited locations like cycle paths and sports facilities.**

WHO

The general population

WHAT

Temperature measurements

WHERE

Frequently visited locations like cycle paths and sports facilities

WHEN

During daytime hours

WHY

To evaluate the exposure in those areas

HOW

Sensors

- **KPI 3: Number of participants involved in testing the proposed solution.**

WHO

Participants

WHAT

People recruitment

WHERE

Frequently visited locations like cycle paths and sports facilities

WHEN

During the trial phase (2025)

WHY

In order to address whether we have reached our goal of recruiting 100 people

HOW

Participant count

- **KPI 4 - Number of participants in the panel for recommendations co-creation (Health experts, local actors and citizens).**

WHO

Panel of co-creators

WHAT

People recruitment

WHERE

In Grenoble area where the experimentations have been carried out

WHEN

After the trial phase (2026)

WHY

To co-create recommendations on physical activity

HOW

Co-creator exchanges through meetings and working groups

- **KPI 5 - Number of recommendations validated by the panel of co-creators**

WHO

Panel of co-creators

WHAT

Create relevant recommendations for outdoor sport in healthy conditions

WHERE

In Grenoble area where the experimentations have been carried out

WHEN

After the trial phase (2026)

WHY

To get multiple point of views on

HOW

Recommendations created, evaluated, and validated by the panel of cocreators

4. Assessment: How to specifically measure the success or failure of each KPI

4.1- VECTRACK- IRIDEON

- **KPI 1- Number of total mosquitos caught**

Make a follow-up on the abundance of at least one mosquito genus (males and females) during a whole mosquito season.

- **KPI 2- Number of detected peaks of mosquito activity**

Detect at least two peaks of mosquito population of at least a mosquito genus (males and females), during a whole mosquito season.

- **KPI 3- Incidence of mosquito-borne diseases (e.g., Dengue, WNV, Malaria) in mosquito and human populations**

Execute at least one laboratory analysis of samples of female mosquitoes, or acquire a public report about incidence of mosquito-borne diseases.

- **KPI 4- Mosquito-borne disease infections abroad or in Demo site: imported vs autochthonous cases**

Acquire a public report about incidence of mosquito-borne diseases, from either local health entities or the ECDC- European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control.

- **KPI 5- Detection of mosquitos and eggs/larvae in breeding sites, performed by field technicians**

Detect at least one suspicious breeding site for each chosen adult sampling area (selected spot to place a trap) in each mosquito season

- **KPI 6- Data from mosquito alerts (sightings, bites, breeding sites)**

Acquire citizen reported data in the area of concern (or in a close-by region) from a free app like "Mosquito Alert" (<https://www.mosquitoalert.com/en/>).

4.2 Indoor environmental quality (IEQ) monitoring method- CSTB

- **KPI 1- Thermal environment**

The success or failure of this KPI is measured by assessing the probability of the guideline values being exceeded.

- **KPI 2- Indoor air quality**

The success or failure of this KPI is measured by assessing the probability of the guideline values being exceeded.

- **KPI 3- Indoor air resilience**

The success or failure of this KPI is measured by assessing the amplitude of impact and the response and recovery of the building's indoor environment following an extreme weather event.

4.3 SURVIVAL- UMIT

- **KPI 1- Vector Modelling**

Biological plausibility: The model must align with the known life cycle and behaviour of *Aedes aegypti*.

Reproducibility: Running the model under the same conditions should yield consistent outputs.

Adaptability: The ability of the model to incorporate new data (e.g. updated habitats or climate trends) without loss of stability.

- **KPI 2- Climatic Data**

Data completeness: The coverage of all necessary variables (temperature, humidity, rainfall, solar radiation) for each day in the modelled year.

Temporal resolution: Ensure daily granularity is maintained.

Spatial accuracy: Data must match the geographical resolution of the study area (e.g. regional level for Tirol).

- **KPI 3- Simulation Scenarios**

Scenario coverage: A diverse and representative range of scenarios is

Internal consistency: Scenario parameters must logically align (e.g. increased temperature should accelerate vector development).

Comparability: Scenarios should be comparable against each other with clear, measurable outcomes.

Sensitivity to change: The Model responds to scenario changes (e.g. observable impact on vector population or spread).

Accuracy of prediction: Compare modelled vector presence with known occurrence data or expert assessments (e.g. matching predicted hotspots with known high-risk areas).

- **KPI 4- Analysis and Visualization of Scenarios**

Clarity: Visual outputs (maps, graphs) clearly communicate differences between scenarios and regions.

Interpretability: Statistical results are understandable and actionable for stakeholders.

Accuracy: Visualizations must correctly reflect the underlying data without distortion.

Insight generation: Enables identification of risk areas, trends, and potential interventions.

4.4 SENTINEL - ARIA

- **KPI 1- Real-time monitoring of air pollution exposure.**

The success of this KPI is measured by the number of regulatory threshold exceedance alerts (ozone, NO₂, PM) generated automatically via the continuous measurement platform. An annual analysis is used to assess the frequency, seasonality and relevance of alerts. A low rate of unjustified alerts and a good response from hospital services are indicators of success.

- **KPI 2- Air pollution exposure forecast.**

This KPI is evaluated by the rate of agreement between the forecasts produced by atmospheric dispersion modelling and the actual measurements recorded on the site

of interest. A key indicator is the number of correctly anticipated pollution peaks that can lead to adjustments in the organization of care (e.g. postponement of consultations, increased ventilation). An annual analysis validates the performance of the forecasting system.

- **KPI 3- Allergenic pollen peak detection through real-time monitoring.**

The success of this KPI is based on the ability to detect ragweed pollen peaks in real time via continuous measurement sensors (e.g. pollen sensors) and to generate relevant alerts. Key indicators can include the concordance rate between the alerts issued by a forecasting model and local measurements, and the number of alerts sent to health establishments. An annual analysis after pollen season, focusing on the period from mid-August to mid-September, is used to assess the performance of the system.

- **KPI 4- Critical periods for air quality.**

This KPI is measured by analysing annual trends in air quality and pollen concentrations over several seasons, highlighting critical periods. Success depends on the ability to identify significant changes (increase, decrease, temporal shift).

- **KPI 5- Ragweed pollen sources mapping.**

This key performance indicator is measured by identifying local plants responsible for pollen concentrations, and therefore allergies.

4.5 LIFE RESYSTAL ecosystem- NCSR

- **KPI 1- Number of climate risk assessments conducted.**

Estimate the full range of assessment, normalize them with the maximum number of analysis made by one demonstrator in the project and provide a scoring value.

- **KPI 2 - Vulnerability level of different locations and per category.**

Finalize the analysis in the LIFE RESYSTAL platform

- **KPI 3 - Impact level of different locations and per category.**

Finalize the analysis in the LIFE RESYSTAL platform

- **KPI 4 - Risk level of different locations and per category.**

Finalize the analysis in the LIFE RESYSTAL platform

4.6 MenKorn CALL- CRISISOFT

- **KPI 1- Device – Situation information**

The success or failure of this indicator is measured by the overall organization of the crisis in terms of its size and scope.

- **KPI 2- Device - Areas & managers**

The success or failure of this indicator is measured by the implementation of operational zones in the field, as close as possible to the crisis.

- **KPI 3- Device - Number of Accounts Alerted**

The success or failure of this indicator is measured by the coordination of the various players alerted, for strategic decision-making.

- **KPI 4- Device – Territorial impact**

The success or failure of this indicator is measured by the extent to which other healthcare facilities are called upon to treat the flow of patients and the pathologies identified.

- **KPI 5- Handrail – Statistics**

The success or failure of this indicator is measured by the relevance of exchanges and the transmission of information in real time to ensure that key information for decision-making is immediately available.

- **KPI 6- Handrail – Journal**

The success or failure of this indicator is measured by the relevance of exchanges and the transmission of information in real time to ensure that key information for decision-making is immediately available.

- **KPI 7- Staff – Profiles of committed and operational staff**

The success or failure of this indicator is measured by the quantity and quality of the professionals involved in dealing with the crisis as effectively as possible.

- **KPI 8- Vehicles – Stock**

The success or failure of this indicator is measured by the quantity and quality of the vehicles used to deal with the crisis as effectively as possible.

4.7 Disaster preparedness checklist- UPO

- **KPI 1 – User-perceived accuracy level of the Checklist in identifying items that are lacking or suboptimal for disaster preparedness**

Success: > 50% users evaluating the accuracy level as above a certain benchmark (i.e. 5 out of 10).

Failure: < 50% users evaluating the accuracy level as above a certain benchmark (i.e. 5 out of 10).

How to measure success or failure?

Track results of monitoring survey over multiple assessments.

- **KPI 2 – Time spent for filling up the Checklist**

Success: > 50% users complete the Checklist within a benchmark (i.e. 1-7 days).

Failure: < 50% users complete the Checklist within a benchmark (i.e. 1-7 days).

How to measure success or failure?

Track results of monitoring survey over multiple assessments.

- **KPI 3 – User-perceived increase in disaster preparedness awareness after using the Checklist**

Success: > 50% users perceive an increase in disaster preparedness awareness after using the Checklist

Failure: < 50% users perceive an increase in disaster preparedness awareness after using the Checklist

How to measure success or failure?

Track results of monitoring survey over multiple assessments.

4.8 Physical activity recommendations- UGA

- **KPI 1: Levels of air pollution in high-traffic areas such as cycle paths and sports facilities.**

Air pollution measurements obtained for outings related to the clinical research project underlying Physical activity recommendations.

- **KPI 2: Temperature measurements at frequently visited locations like cycle paths and sports facilities.**

Temperature measurements obtained for outings related to the clinical research project underlying Physical activity recommendations.

- **KPI 3: Number of participants involved in testing the proposed solution.**

Participant count = 100 = success

- **KPI 4 - Number of participants in the panel for recommendations co-creation (Health experts, local actors and citizens).**

At least 3 to 5 different s of co-creators for the recommendations.

- **KPI 5 - Number of recommendations validated by the panel of co-creators**

Formulate a minimum of 5 key and meaningful recommendations that can be sub-divided.

5. Assessment: Define how to affect each KPI positively and ensure that the targets are met.

5.1- VECTRACK- IRIDEON

- **KPI 1- Number of total mosquitos caught**

Make a careful selection of the sampling sites to place the mosquito traps with the VECTRACK sensors, following the instructions of the manufacturer of the commercial traps. A poorly selected sampling site, or inadequate installation of the traps, can lead to scarce or no captures of adult mosquitoes.

- **KPI 2- Number of detected peaks of mosquito activity**

Place traps in places with nearby potential breeding-sites duly identified.

- **KPI 3- Incidence of mosquito-borne diseases (e.g., Dengue, WNV, Malaria) in mosquito and human populations**

Coordinate with local public health authorities to understand how to acquire public data about incidence of mosquito-borne diseases. Consult the reports published by the ECDC- European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control.

- **KPI 4- Mosquito-borne disease infections abroad or in Demo site: imported vs autochthonous cases**

Consult the reports published by local public health authorities and/or the ECDC- European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control.

- **KPI 5- Detection of mosquitos and eggs/larvae in breeding sites, performed by field technicians**

Make periodical visits to sites after rainfall, to detect any elements with standing water.

- **KPI 6- Data from mosquito alerts (sightings, bites, breeding sites)**

Install and use the free app “Mosquito Alert” (<https://www.mosquitoalert.com/en/>).

5.2 Indoor environmental quality (IEQ) monitoring method- CSTB

- **KPI 1- Thermal environment**

Optimizing the building's usage, including the function of the HVAC system, can improve the thermal environment.

- **KPI 2- Indoor air quality**

Optimizing the building's usage, including ventilation and air purification, can improve the indoor air quality.

- **KPI 3- Indoor air resilience**

Optimizing the building's usage, including the function of the HVAC system, can improve the indoor air resilience.

5.3 SURVIVAL- UMIT

- **KPI 1- Vector Modelling**

Use validated biological parameters (development thresholds, life cycle durations) from peer-reviewed literature.

- **KPI 2- Climatic Data**

Source data from reliable providers; Standardize data formats and units before integration. Ensure temporal and spatial alignment between data and the model's needs (e.g., daily resolution, consistent geolocation).

- **KPI 3- Simulation Scenarios**

Define clear objectives for each scenario (e.g., climate change impact, transport-based introduction, control strategies). Ensure parameters are internally consistent and biologically plausible. Base scenarios on evidence (e.g., IPCC temperature projections, known traffic routes, demographic distributions)

- **KPI 4- Analysis and Visualization of Scenarios**

Use intuitive/simple GIS visualizations that clearly show spatial dynamics of vector risk; Standardize visualization templates (colors, scales, legends) for comparability.

5.4 SENTINEL- ARIA

- **KPI 1- Real-time monitoring of air pollution exposure.**

To improve this KPI, it is essential to ensure the reliability and ongoing maintenance of sensors, and to incorporate alerts into hospital protocols. Raising staff awareness of how to interpret alerts and coordinating with technical services to adapt ventilation or internal movements can reinforce the impact of this data.

- **KPI 2- Air pollution exposure forecast.**

To improve this KPI, the models need to be regularly calibrated with measured local data, input parameters (emissions, weather) need to be continually updated, and hospital teams need to be trained in how to use the forecasts. Incorporating forecasts into hospital planning tools (e.g. dashboards, internal alerts) enables critical episodes to be anticipated effectively.

- **KPI 3- Allergenic pollen peak detection through real-time monitoring.**

To strengthen this KPI, we recommend increasing the density of local sensors, cross-referencing pollen data with sales of antihistamines or allergy consultations, and disseminating alerts via appropriate channels (SMS, hospital platforms). Collaboration with pharmacies and public health services can also improve responsiveness to allergen peaks.

- **KPI 4- Critical periods for air quality.**

To improve this KPI, it is essential to maintain rigorous data (monitoring and forecast) collection over several years. It is also necessary to ensure that health services can use these past analyses for future analyses in order to anticipate critical periods.

- **KPI 5- Ragweed pollen sources mapping.**

To improve this KPI, it is essential to maintain rigorous data collection over several years, map local pollen sources and implement targeted reduction measures (e.g. ragweed removal). A statistical analysis of the location of sources based on measurements can also be carried out for the removal of ragweed. Collaboration with local authorities helps to increase the effectiveness of the measures taken and to assess their long-term impact.

5.5 LIFE RESYSTAL ecosystem- NCSR D

- **KPI 1- Number of climate risk assessments conducted.**

- not applicable

- **KPI 2 - Vulnerability level of different locations and per category.**

- not applicable

- **KPI 3 - Impact level of different locations and per category.**

- not applicable

- **KPI 4 - Risk level of different locations and per category.**

- not applicable

5.6 MenKorn CALL- CRISISOFT

- **KPI 1- Device – Situation information**

By regularly updating key information.

- **KPI 2- Device - Areas & managers**

By adapting the field system as the crisis evolves.

- **KPI 3- Device - Number of Accounts Alerted**

By adjusting alerting to the people empowered to make effective decisions within the scope of responsibility.

- **KPI 4- Device – Territorial impact**

By requesting support from other healthcare facilities to handle the flow and type of pathology.

- **KPI 5- Handrail – Statistics**

Ensuring relevant communication to the entire community empowered to intervene in the crisis.

- **KPI 6- Handrail – Journal**

Ensuring relevant communication to the entire community empowered to intervene in the crisis.

- **KPI 7- Staff – Profiles of committed and operational staff**

By increasing or decreasing the number of staff to be deployed in the field, depending on how the crisis evolves.

- **KPI 8- Vehicles – Stock**

By increasing or decreasing the number of vehicles to be deployed in the field, depending on how the crisis evolves.

5.7 Disaster preparedness checklist- UPO

- **KPI 1 – User-perceived accuracy level of the Checklist in identifying items that are lacking or suboptimal for disaster preparedness**

The KPI is more likely to succeed if the Checklist is developed through an evidence-based approach, created starting from existing validated tools, and co-created with end-users.

- **KPI 2 – Time spent for filling up the Checklist**

Be available to support demonstration and replication sites in case of difficulties, promote the development of local expertise and ownership of the tool, and encourage peer learning to gradually build a network of experts.

- **KPI 3 – User-perceived increase in disaster preparedness awareness after using the Checklist**

Encourage the use of the Checklist not only as a monitoring tool but also as an advocacy instrument to raise awareness in the health sector of disaster preparedness in response to the expected increase in EWEs.

5.8 Physical activity recommendations- UGA

- **KPI 1: Levels of air pollution in high-traffic areas such as cycle paths and sports facilities.**

Air pollution measurements available for >75% of outings

D3.1 – Monitoring protocols and methodology for solutions' effectiveness assessment

- **KPI 2: Temperature measurements at frequently visited locations like cycle paths and sports facilities.**

Temperature measurements available for >75% of outings

- **KPI 3: Number of participants involved in testing the proposed solution.**

Number of participants = 100

- **KPI 4 - Number of participants in the panel for recommendations co-creation (Health experts, local actors and citizens).**

At least 3 to 5 different profiles of co-creators for the recommendations.

- **KPI 5 - Number of recommendations validated by the panel of co-creators**

Formulate a minimum of 5 key and meaningful recommendations that can be subdivided.

B. Training Evaluation

1. Objectives and steps of the evaluation

The **objectives** of the evaluation of the training are **five**:

- ★ Measure overall learner satisfaction with the training program (surveys, stars-scale) (**Objective 1, O.1**)
- ★ Identify areas for improvement in course content and delivery (surveys, tracking report) (**Objective 2, O.2**)
- ★ Gauge learner engagement (tracking report, interviews with demosite leaders) (**Objective 3, O.3**)
- ★ Evaluate the effectiveness of instructional materials (surveys, tracking report). Including clarity and feasibility of the materials and impact on the professional role. (**Objective 4, O.4**)
- ★ Monitor progress over time (tracking report) (**Objective 5, O.5**)

The **steps** to evaluate the training are the following four:

The ex-ante evaluation basically consists of the **Training Needs Assessment (TNA)** presented in the Internal Report 1.4 (submitted on month 11, April 2025) and the Training Co-creation Activities detailed in the Deliverable 2.4 (submitted on month 15, August 2025). The TNA presents the needs, gaps in knowledge and format preferences of the healthcare professionals through the use of co-creation methodologies namely surveys and interviews. **Co-creation workshops**, together with iterative feedback from

D3.1 – Monitoring protocols and methodology for solutions' effectiveness assessment

climate-change and health experts, were employed to co-create the final training syllabus.

The following steps, **2. Intermediary** and **3. Final evaluations** consist of **satisfaction surveys** for every module, the **activity tracking report** provided by the online Learning Management System (LMS) and of the **monitoring interviews** with the demosite leaders. The step 2 will be finalised after the demonstration sites test the training and UDEUSTO gathers the results. Step 3 will use the same approach as step 2, but in the replicator sites. The last step, Step 4, includes support during the **drafting** of the final document.

Steps 2 and 3 will follow the objectives presented at the beginning of the section. These objectives correspond to the levels 1 and 2 of the Kirkpatrick's evaluation method¹.

The **level 1: Reactions** corresponds to the objectives 2, 3, 4 and 5 focused on the overall satisfaction of the participants, answering the question "How did participants feel about the programme?". This level assesses the **Perceived Training Efficiency** taking into account more technical aspects of the training, such as format or methodology².

¹ Kirkpatrick, J. D., & Kirkpatrick, W. K. (2016). *Kirkpatrick's four levels of training evaluation*. Association for Talent Development

² Giangreco, A., Sebastiano, A., & Peccei, R. (2009). Trainees' reactions to training: an analysis of the factors affecting overall satisfaction with training. *The international journal of human resource management*, 20(1), 96-111.

On the other hand, the **level 2: Learning** corresponds to the objectives 1 and 4, focused on the short-term changes, answering the question “To what extent did participants improve knowledge, skills and change attitudes as a result of the training?”. This level focuses on the **Perceived Usefulness of the Training** having into account the usefulness and relevance of the training content and on the evaluation of the improvement of professional competencies³.

2. Methodology for the evaluation of the training

Survey

Completing surveys can impose a burden on participants and increase attrition rates. To mitigate this, we designed a survey to be administered only once, immediately after the completion of each module. Questions 1–3 ask participants to rate their knowledge/confidence/motivation before and after the training, allowing us to assess perceived changes in these dimensions. Questions 4–6, by contrast, inquire solely

³ Gil-Lacruz, M., Gracia-Pérez, M. L., & Gil-Lacruz, A. I. (2019). Learning by doing and training satisfaction: An evaluation by health care professionals. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 16(8), 1397.

about participants' status following module completion⁴. The answers of the survey will be gathered either using the Qualtrics Platform or the survey tool included in the Moodle LMS.

The survey will include the following questions, with responses provided on an ordinal scale:

For questions 1 to 3, please use the following rating scale

1	2	3	4	5
None or very low level	Low level	Moderate level	High level	Very high level

Please indicate your level on the following dimensions both before and after completing the training module.

Before the training

After the training

1 2 3 4 5

1. Your knowledge of the content covered in this module.

1 2 3 4 5

1 2 3 4 5

2. Your confidence in applying the module's content in your personal or professional life

1 2 3 4 5

1 2 3 4 5

3. Your motivation to learn about the module's content

1 2 3 4 5

For questions 4 to 6, please check the appropriate option using the following rating scale

1	2	3	4	5
Very dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very satisfied

⁴ Little, T. D., Chang, R., Gorrall, B. K., Waggenspack, L., Fukuda, E., Allen, P. J., & Noam, G. G. (2020). The retrospective pretest–posttest design redux: On its validity as an alternative to traditional pretest–posttest measurement. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 44(2), 175-183.

4. How would you rate the quality of the module's content? 1 2 3 4 5
5. How satisfied are you with the materials used for learning (videos, readings, documents)? 1 2 3 4 5
6. How satisfied are you with the learning structure followed (context, reflection, conceptualise, experiment, evaluation)? 1 2 3 4 5

Questions 1 to 3 address the **Level 2: Learning** of Kirkpatrick's evaluation method, and objectives 2 (Identify areas for improvement in course content) and 4 (Evaluate the effectiveness of instructional materials. Including impact on the professional role).

Questions 4 to 6 address the **Level 1: Overall satisfaction** of Kirkpatrick's evaluation method, and objectives 1 (Measure overall learner satisfaction with the training program), 2 (Identify areas for improvement in course delivery), and 4 (Evaluate the effectiveness of instructional materials. Including clarity and feasibility of the materials).

Given that Module 7—"Presentation and Guidelines of Mountadapt's Solutions"—employed a distinct content approach from the other modules, we developed a dedicated survey to evaluate it (sample below). Responses will be collected via the Qualtrics platform or the Moodle LMS survey tool. The survey items align with Kirkpatrick's Level 1: Overall Satisfaction. Upon completing Module 7, learners will rate their satisfaction using the following ordinal scale:

Please check the appropriate option using the following rating scale:

1	2	3	4	5
Very dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very satisfied

1. How would you rate the quality of the module's content?

1 2 3 4 5

2. How satisfied are you with the materials used for learning (videos, readings, documents)?
(List of solutions)

1 2 3 4 5

3. How satisfied are you with the clarity and organisation of the online learning materials (videos, readings, documents, etc.)? (List of solutions)

1 2 3 4 5

For questions 4, please use the following rating scale:

1	2	3	4	5
Not at all relevant	Slightly relevant	Moderately relevant	Very relevant	Extremely relevant

4. How relevant is each of the following solutions to your needs? (List of solutions)

1 2 3 4 5

For question 5, please use the following rating scale:

1	2	3	4	5
None or very low level	Low level	Moderate level	High level	Very high level

5. To what extent do you believe this module has positively impacted your professional practice?

1 2 3 4 5

6. Select the solutions you would like to implement in your region. (List of solutions)

Activity Tracking Report

This report will be provided by the Moodle LMS, and will include the following KPI:

KPI 1 (O.3) – Number of beneficiaries of the training, disaggregated by:

- *Affiliation*: academia, government local, government state, government national, international organisation, NGO, private sector, regional organisation
- *Location*: Austria/France/Romania/Slovenia/Andorra/Germany/Romania

KPI 2 (O.2, O.4) – Drop-off points: where users stop engaging

KPI 3 (O.3, O.4, O.5)– Completion rate (% of participants who finished the module)

KPI 4 (O.2, O.4)– Number of clicks to arrive to key information (to measure ease of navigation)

KPI 5 (O.3, O5) – Number of logins

KPI 6 (O.3, O.4, O.5) – Revisit rate (returning to previous modules/pages)

KPI 7 (O.4)– Performance in the final module evaluation assessments

These KPIs will feed into the objectives 2, 3, 4, and 5. KPI 2, 3, and 4 will provide the input to identify areas for improvement in course content and delivery (**Objective 2**). KPI 1, 5, 6 will help assess learner engagement (**Objective 3**). KPI 2, 3, 4, 6 and 7, will help to evaluate the effectiveness of instructional materials. Including clarity and feasibility of the materials (**Objective 4**). Finally, KPI 3, 5 and 6 will help monitor progress over time (**Objective 5**).

Monitoring interviews

The monitoring interviews will be conducted with the demosite leaders before and during the launch of the training as part of the planning for the training dissemination and engagement. The same process will be carried out for the launch in the replicators. The interviews will serve to monitor the efforts of the demosites and Mountadapt's communications on the dissemination of the training, and will be quantified with the following KPIs:

KPI 1 (O.3) – Number of people invited:

- *Definition:* actual number of individuals reached with communications about the training.
- *How to measure:* individuals can be reached through two channels:
 - **Directly** by the Demosite Leader organisation (based on the number of people they invited).
 - **Indirectly** via the stakeholders contacted by the Demosite Leader (who will report how many people they invited).
 - The Demosite Leader must combine both numbers and report the total to UDEUSTO.
- *Why it matters:* measures how far the message has spread.

KPI 2 (O.3) – Dissemination channels used:

- *Definition:* document the specific communication channels used to promote the training within each target region.
- *How to measure:* since the target audience is region-specific, the main channels should be related to the Mountadapt Community of Practice (CoP) or internal networks within the demosite region. Mountadapt's social media (website and linkedin) can be used to disseminate the training, always indicating that the target participants are healthcare professionals (healthcare staff, policy-makers and researchers) belonging to the Demosite's regions.
- *Why it matters:* helps quantify the scope and relevance of the dissemination efforts, ensures reaching the intended audience, helps identify strong and weak points in the regional communication strategy.

C. Tailoring of the Impact Assessment framework and application

TransformAr Avoided Damages framework and application

The concept of Damages and Avoid Damages from climate change is developed and defined based on the current literature. As such, damages from climate change encompass a broad range of adverse impacts that are not adequately mitigated or adapted to, while avoided damages represent the benefits of effective mitigation and adaptation efforts, preventing potential future impacts. Following the definitions, an assessment framework was introduced that provides generalized quantification of avoided damages.

The framework is based on estimating the current situation (baseline) and the potential effectiveness of solutions implemented at demonstrator level to cope with climate change impacts. The difference between the baseline and the effectiveness of the solutions describes the level of the damages that have been avoided. The same can be applied for the future climate scenarios, thus, estimating the avoided damages from climate change. Important and noted is that the framework needs to be applied for each climate stressor / hazard separately. In addition, to accommodate the potential lack of available data, two version of the approach is introduced; (i) High data

availability - KPI based approach and (ii) Sparse data – High level approach (see Section below). For both cases, the impact quantification can be extracted via tools and models or by expected estimation from experts. The expert input can be a percentage estimation of the amount of change in the KPI used, based on their experience, knowledge, literature review or best practices. The aforementioned approach has been developed in TransformAr project and further being developed in MOUNTADAPT project.

1. Validate the KPIs: Check which KPIs from D1.1 per solution can be quantified and when

1.1 VECTRACK- IRIDEON

- **KPI 1- Number of total mosquitos caught**

Mosquito abundance can be easily quantified using the VECTRACK software, anytime during the mosquito season.

- **KPI 2- Number of detected peaks of mosquito activity**

Mosquito activity peaks can be easily quantified using the VECTRACK software, anytime during the mosquito season.

- **KPI 3- Incidence of mosquito-borne diseases (e.g., Dengue, WNV, Malaria) in mosquito and human populations**

Consult local public health authorities and the reports published by the ECDC-European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control. This can be done as soon as possible.

- **KPI 4- Mosquito-borne disease infections abroad or in Demo site: imported vs autochthonous cases**

Consult local public health authorities and the reports published by the ECDC-European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control. This can be done as soon as possible.

- **KPI 5- Detection of mosquitos and eggs/larvae in breeding sites, performed by field technicians**

Field technicians of the demo sites must detect and count the breeding sites found in and around the areas where traps are deployed: before and after deployment, and especially after each rainfall episode.

- **KPI 6- Data from mosquito alerts (sightings, bites, breeding sites)**

Install and use the free app “Mosquito Alert” (<https://www.mosquitoalert.com/en/>). This can be done as soon as possible.

1.2 Indoor environmental quality (IEQ) monitoring method- CSTB

The KPIs should be assessed after the solution has been implemented at the demonstration site and the measurement data has been collected and validated.

1.3 SURVIVAL- UMIT

For the survival modelling component, the responsible experts are Bernhard Pfeifer, Alexandra Schwaiger and Marco Schweitzer, who have completed the necessary validation and integration steps for this KPI.

1.4 SENTINEL- ARIA

- **KPI 1- Real-time monitoring of air pollution exposure.**

The data is available continuously via the AirAdvanced® Sentinel platform. Pollution peaks are frequent in summer (ozone) and winter (PM).

The total number of alerts can be quantified, with an annual analysis proposed to assess the frequency, temporal distribution and relevance of alerts.

- **KPI 2- Air pollution exposure forecast.**

Forecasts from atmospheric modelling are also available continuously. Their validation is based on comparison with actual measurements. An annual analysis will assess the reliability of the forecasts and their operational usefulness.

- **KPI 3- Allergenic pollen peak detection through real-time monitoring.**

Pollen data is measured continuously and can be accessed via a platform. The ragweed peak is generally between mid-August and mid-September. The number of alerts generated during this period can be analysed each December to assess the performance of the alert system.

- **KPI 4- Critical periods for air quality.**

The analysis requires several seasons of data. A quantified assessment is planned to measure trends, inter-annual variations and the impact of corrective actions.

- **KPI 5- Ragweed pollen sources mapping.**

The analysis requires peaks of pollen measurements. A quantified assessment is planned to identify local ragweed plants and the impact of corrective actions.

1.5 LIFE RESYSTAL ecosystem- NCSR

- **KPI 1- Number of climate risk assessments conducted.**

Validated and statistics under way

- **KPI 2 - Vulnerability level of different locations and per category.**

Validated and statistics under way

- **KPI 3 - Impact level of different locations and per category.**

Validated and statistics under way

- **KPI 4 - Risk level of different locations and per category.**

Validated and statistics under way

1.6 MenKorn CALL- CRISISOFT

The definition of the indicators put in place are based on Crisisoft's expertise in terms of crisis management, but also sharing with the pilots during the demonstration phases, needs analysis and implementation of the solution.

1.7 Disaster preparedness checklist- UPO

- **KPI 1 – User-perceived accuracy level of the Checklist in identifying items that are lacking or suboptimal for disaster preparedness** (slightly modified from D1.1)

An initial quantification of accuracy can be led by the solution provider when promoting the completion of the Checklist by the demonstration and replication sites. It will then be suggested to representatives of the health systems in the demonstration and replication sites to keep on completing the monitoring survey every time they complete the Checklist.

- **KPI 2 – Time spent for filling up the Checklist**

An initial measurement of the time spent filling out the Checklist can be led by the solution provider after completion of the Checklist. It will then be suggested to representatives of the health systems in the demonstration and replication sites to keep on completing the monitoring survey every time they complete the Checklist.

- **KPI 3 – User-perceived increase in disaster preparedness awareness after using the Checklist** (slightly modified from D1.1)

An initial measurement of the time spent filling out the Checklist can be led by the solution provider after completion of the Checklist. It will then be suggested to representatives of the health systems in the demonstration and replication sites to keep on completing the monitoring survey every time they complete the Checklist.

1.8 Physical activity recommendations- UGA

- **KPI 1: Levels of air pollution in high-traffic areas such as cycle paths and sports facilities.**

Air pollution measurements available for >75% of outings

- **KPI 2: Temperature measurements at frequently visited locations like cycle paths and sports facilities.**

Temperature measurements available for >75% of outings

- **KPI 3: Number of participants involved in testing the proposed solution.**

Number of participants = 100

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- **KPI 4 - Number of participants in the panel for recommendations co-creation (Health experts, local actors and citizens).**

At least 3 to 5 different profiles of co-creators for the recommendations

- **KPI 5 - Number of recommendations validated by the panel of co-creators**

Formulate 5 to 10 key and meaningful recommendations that can be sub-divided

2. Filter the KPIs: Do you believe the selected quantifiable KPIs will potentially be affected due to Climate Change in the future?

2.1 VECTRACK- IRIDEON

- **KPI 1- Number of total mosquitos caught**

Mosquito abundance is expected to increase with Climate Change.

- **KPI 2- Number of detected peaks of mosquito activity**

Mosquito activity peaks are expected to increase, in frequency and intensity, with Climate Change.

- **KPI 3- Incidence of mosquito-borne diseases (e.g., Dengue, WNV, Malaria) in mosquito and human populations**

Incidence of mosquito-borne diseases is expected to increase with Climate Change

- **KPI 4- Mosquito-borne disease infections abroad or in Demo site: imported vs autochthonous cases**

The yearly number of imported and autochthonous cases are expected to increase with Climate Change.

- **KPI 5- Detection of mosquitos and eggs/larvae in breeding sites, performed by field technicians**

The yearly number of breeding sites detected are expected to increase with Climate Change.

- **KPI 6- Data from mosquito alerts (sightings, bites, breeding sites)**

The yearly reports from citizens about number of mosquito sights, bites and breeding sites are expected to increase with Climate Change.

2.2 Indoor environmental quality (IEQ) monitoring method- CSTB

The three KPIs can be quantified under current climate scenarios in existing buildings. The results cannot be quantitatively projected to future climate scenarios. To enable a quantitative projection, it is necessary to simulate the building's indoor environmental performance under future climate conditions using numerical tools.

2.3 SURVIVAL- UMIT

No, KPIs are not impacted by climate change.

2.4 SENTINEL- ARIA

- **KPI 1- Real-time monitoring of air pollution exposure.**

Yes, this KPI is very likely to be affected by climate change. Rising temperatures, more frequent heatwaves and stagnant air in urban areas encourage the formation of ground-level ozone and the accumulation of fine particles. This could lead to an increase in the number of threshold exceedance alerts, particularly in summer and winter, making this KPI even more critical for hospital management.

- **KPI 2- Air pollution exposure forecast.**

Yes, forecasting models will have to incorporate more extreme climate scenarios and more variable weather conditions. Climate change could modify atmospheric dispersion patterns, making forecasts more complex but also more necessary to anticipate pollution episodes.

- **KPI 3- Allergenic pollen peak detection through real-time monitoring.**

Yes, climate change has a direct influence on pollen production: longer seasons, higher concentrations, and the geographical spread of allergenic species such as ragweed. This could lead to an increase in the frequency and intensity of allergenic peaks, making this KPI essential for public health.

- **KPI 4- Critical periods for air quality.**

Yes, for the same reason as KPI 1.

- **KPI 5- Ragweed pollen sources mapping.**

Yes, for the same reason as KPI 3.

2.5 LIFE RESYSTAL ecosystem- NCSR

- **KPI 1- Number of climate risk assessments conducted.**

It is incorporated in the process.

- **KPI 2 - Vulnerability level of different locations and per category.**

It is incorporated in the process.

- **KPI 3 - Impact level of different locations and per category.**

It is incorporated in the process.

- **KPI 4 - Risk level of different locations and per category.**

It is incorporated in the process.

2.6 MenKorn CALL- CRISISOFT

No, KPIs are not impacted by climate change. These indicators enable effective crisis management, and not just in the context of climate change.

2.7 Disaster preparedness checklist- UPO

Increase in EWEs may drive the use of the Checklist, as its short-term utility becomes apparent, and it can be consulted to develop new disaster response plans/protocols (potentially influencing **KPI 2** and **KPI 3**).

Similarly, exposure to recurring EWEs may encourage participation in the training package due to its short-term relevance and direct interest (affecting **KPI 4**).

Nevertheless, frequent responses to EWEs may increase familiarity with the topics, reducing the motivation for additional courses on the same subjects due to existing experiential knowledge (potentially influencing **KPI 4** and **KPI 6**).

2.8 Physical activity recommendations- UGA

- **KPI 1- Levels of air pollution in high-traffic areas such as cycle paths and sports facilities.**

The KPI could potentially be impacted due to climate change. Mountain valleys like Grenoble face complex and mixed prospects for air pollution evolution under climate change, with competing factors that will determine the net impact on air quality in these topographically sensitive regions.

- **KPI 2- Temperature measurements at frequently visited locations like cycle paths and sports facilities.**

The KPI could potentially be impacted by the future climate changes. Average temperatures did increase noticeably in the last decade, and the tendency is most likely heading to the same direction, with a warmer environment most of the time

- **KPI 3- Number of participants involved in testing the proposed solution.**

The number of participants involved is more dependant of the recruiting campaign than the climate change.

- **KPI 4 - Number of participants in the panel for recommendations co-creation (Health experts, local actors and citizens).**

The panel of co-creation can be affected by the interest in actions to take with climate change

- **KPI 5 - Number of recommendations validated by the panel of co-creators**

The recommendations can be affected by the climate change scenario.

D. Next steps

Each demonstration site will implement the selected solutions, supported by tailored training programmes. Their deployment will be systematically monitored and assessed in Task 3.3, led by UGA, using the KPI-based protocol and methodology established in this deliverable (D3.1).

In parallel, D3.1 will guide the collection of site-specific data feeding into the Lean Development Process, enabling refinement, improvement, and optimisation of the solutions during Task 3.3.

Furthermore, the information compiled in D3.1 for tailoring the TADA framework will serve as the basis for conducting a Health Impact Assessment (HIA) and evaluating overall solution effectiveness in Task 3.4, under the leadership of NCSR D.

The consolidated findings from Tasks 3.3 and 3.4 will be presented in Deliverable 3.2: Solutions Assessment and Improvement Report.

E. Conclusions

Deliverable D3.1 has established the monitoring protocols, training evaluation methodology, and tailored TADA framework necessary for assessing the effectiveness of Mountadapt solutions. Together, these elements provide a coherent foundation for data collection, performance monitoring, and impact assessment across demonstration sites.

The outputs of this deliverable will directly support the implementation and evaluation of solutions in Task 3.3, while also enabling the Health Impact Assessment and effectiveness assessment in Task 3.4. As such, D3.1 represents a critical step in ensuring that project solutions are systematically monitored, continuously improved, and assessed towards their contribution to climate resilience.

The forthcoming Deliverable 3.2 will consolidate these assessments, providing evidence-based insights to guide solution optimisation and long-term uptake.

MOUNTADAPT is a Horizon Europe project aiming to boost the community-driven resilience of the health system in European mountain areas, mitigating the impact of climate change on public health. Leveraging the expertise of 27 partners, including healthcare facilities, public authorities, innovators, and researchers, MOUNTADAPT aims to develop solutions and strategies to enhance healthcare climate adaptation and safeguard the health and well-being of communities living in mountain regions.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.